

STUDENTS' ORAL PRESENTATION PROBLEMS AND TEACHER'S ROLE IN THEIR SOLUTIONS

Nasirova Moira Hamroyevna

Buxoro viloyati G'ijduvon tumanidagi

2-son maktab internat Ingliz tili o'qituvchisi.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola o'quvchilarning og'zaki taqdimoti ahamiyati va uning qiyinchiliklari, hamda ularni yechishda o'qituvchining o'rni haqidadir.

Kalit so'zlar: og'zaki nutq, qiyinchilik, yechim, nutq qo'rquvi, tilni o'qitish, darsni rejalashtirish, baholash.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена важности устной презентации учащихся и ее трудностям, а также роли учителя в их решении.

Ключевые слова: устная речь, трудности, решение, боязнь речи, обучение языку, планирование урока, оценка.

Annotation. The present article deals with the importance of oral presentation of learners and its challenges, as well as teacher's role in their solutions.

Key words: oral presentation, challenge, solution, speech anxiety, language teaching, lesson planning, evaluation.

The first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Abduganievich Karimov speaking about the future of Uzbekistan underlined, that «Harmonious generation is the future guarantee of prosperity».

It is our task, to prepare and teach professionally competent and energetic personnel, real patriots to see them in the world depository of science and culture. In this plan the national program about training personnel was worked out on the formation of new generation of specialist. «With the high common and professionally culture, creative and social activity, with the ability to orientate in the social and political life independently, capable to raise and solve the problems to the perspective⁵».

Oral presentation is not an essay task. For most of students, moreover, EFL are not able to speak with English language with a fluent manner. According to Baker «speaking to group is notoriously stressful activity» so, the delivery of oral presentation can face some problems that is particularly for all EFL.

Speech anxiety is a normal and natural reaction that everyone can have it, when speak in public. According to the Book of lists, 51 percent of adults rate fear of public speaking a head of the fear of death». We can observe speech anxiety in the voice of the presenter. Teacher can easily deal with anxiety by tell their student that anxiety is a normal behavior in order to help them encourage to do their oral presentation without any fear. In addition, if the teacher makes an open decision about speech anxiety students fill that they are not alone.

Some EFL presenters have problem with memorizing information with English so they try to get it by heart. By this way, the audience will feel bored when they have to listen to what

⁵ Kadrlar tayyorlash milliy dasturi: Toshkent 1997, 35- bet.

the speaker said it is look like that they are reading their information «word for- word» from what The memorizing. Moreover if students do not use communication English in their oral presentation and they reading from their memorizing what writing before with a complex sentences, the audience will lose their attention According to King» teacher should constantly remind students of the importance of using communicative English in their presentations and keeping the audience in mind when they prepare.»

One can say that, students' problems with oral presentations should take in consideration. Find a solution of this problem is the rule of both teachers and student.

Many students do not find oral presentation an enjoyable activity. They are afraid when teacher ask them to prepare an oral presentation. According to Cheung, «Many students feel highly nervous about undertaking class presentation» , students have a fear from give an oral presentation because they have not experience. In addition, some of them do not have a confidence in their abilities. When students were been asked about what is effective presentation, they been related it to a clear speech, correct language and when the audience get the main idea. Therefore, it is important to teach student how to make an oral presentation because most of them have not clear ideas about how to do it.

Oral presentations are become more important part of language teaching, especially in Universities. English learners need to be aware with this technique because, it is been considered as an opportunity to improve their English. In the past teachers had been focused on give the learner grammatical rules, vocabulary...etc the communicative approach aim is to teach students how organize the main idea about a given topic in a logical coherent and also its aim to develop the students ability to produce in English with the correct way

Thus, the main purpose of teaching students oral presentation is to help them rejecting the fear of making pronunciation or grammatical error.

The teacher's role is not an easy one because oral presentation is challenging job for teachers like in lesson planning. According to King «teacher move from the traditional role of teacher as an authority expert to the new role of facilitator of learning» In addition, teachers need to prepare their students for this work to develop their interaction skill. According to King, «teachers...still play a key role in the background, as a facilitator, research guides, ultimate references, and source of encouragement.» The teacher's role in oral presentation is an a guide, organizer consultant resource person, and supporter this role involve also organizing into groups, preparing details, more information about the topic, helping them to learn how to use visual aids in their presentation and finally evaluation the students performance.

The first evaluation of an oral presentation is on the speaker itself. The teacher needs to evaluate the performance of these students by looking for their pronunciation, then teacher move to the kind of information that is included in the presentation.

However, in this practice the true evaluation is the speakers' ability to answer the questions, which the audience has been asked.

In conclusion then, it seems there are different purposes which might motivate students to take an English oral presentation class. While these purposes might well include the obvious, learning how to present, they may also include more language oriented purposes. Many students who have spent years studying English may simply wish to keep up their conversational skills and see a presenting course as another way to do this. Teachers need to be aware of this possibility and be more careful when selecting course books. Teachers should try to be positive in their

evaluation and avoid criticism of students' practice that improves by time. In addition, students need to learn how to do it by experience.

References:

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